

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS BRANDED BROADBAND

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Abstract:

This study helps the service providers to adopt scientific strategies to operate in a given market scenario. A study is often commissioned to get an in depth analysis of a specific problem or opportunities. The need and significance of the study is to understand and obtain a clear perspective of the respondents towards branded broadband service providers and their level of satisfaction towards the services provided by branded broadband service providers. The study examines with the different demographics such as age, income, etc. A few reasons that prove the importance and need for the study discussed below. The conclusion is that the management can contact the customer from time to time with suggestions about improved product uses / new product features.

Key Words: Broadband, Demographics & Management

About the Study:

Business environment is today much more complex, competitive and turbulent. As the intense competition becomes a way of doing business it is the customers' who calls the shot in deciding the nature of products and services offered in the market. The customer who calls the shot in deciding the nature of products and services offered in the market. The customers are becoming demanding, dominating and selective. In fact the perception and the expectation of the customers have undergone a sea change. Now-a-days they have also become mere immune to marketers pressure. This means that the advertising and marketing gimmicks for consumers goods will work only when they see real quality in the provision of services at the ground level. Such developments have made the customers the king and as in any monarchy, the king must be flattered.

Perception / Awareness:

Perception is one of the most psychological factors affecting human behavior perception involves selectivity, organizing and interpreting the sensations. The perception is an individual experiences, a situation it may be recognized that is a unique interpretation of the situation, not necessarily on exact recording of the situation the perception may be defined as the process of selection organization and of sensation to provide the meaningful experience for the individual.

Perception is the process by which physical sensations such as sights, sounds and smells are selected, organized and interpreted. The eventual interpretation of a stimulus allows to be assigned meaning. Marketing stimuli have important sensors qualities. People have different thresholds of perceptions.

Statement of the Problem:

This study is a maiden attempt by the researcher to find out the level of awareness and attitude towards branded broadband services existing in Coimbatore city. This study is conducted to find out the various drawbacks of the existing service providers. Based on these issues the researcher attempted to find out actual situation in the market and so this forms the problem statement. Based on these issues, the survey is conducted to find out how far these negatives, impact on the players in market providing broadband services.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the satisfaction of branded broadband
- ✓ To study the problem faced in branded broadband.

Research Methodology:

Sample Size:

Sample size used for the study is 240 respondents from the population of broadband users in the market. The population for this project is individuals which include different people engaged in private employment, public sector, businessmen and others in Coimbatore District, Tamil Nadu.

Sampling Procedure:

The sampling method used in the research is probability sampling. In this method of sampling the technique used is systematic random sampling.

Sources of Data:

The data collected from two major sources:

- ✓ Primary Data
- ✓ Secondary Data

Primary Data Collection: A method of collecting data was through personal interaction by using questionnaire. The questionnaires were filled-in directly by the respondent. The respondents were given brief introduction about the purpose of the survey and questionnaire was put to them. The relevant primary data required for this study were collected from a sample size of 240.

Secondary Data Collection: The secondary data was gathered from the journals, magazines and web sites.

Data Analysis:

The data collected was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using Simple Percentage Method, Weighted Average, Chi-Square Test and ANOVA.

- ✓ Simple Percentage Method
- ✓ Chi-square
- ✓ Weighted mean

Limitations:

Every research study has its own limitations and some of those encountered during the study were listed below:

- ✓ Time limit restricts detailed survey work and opinion collection.
- ✓ This research project has limitations caused by resource constraints. The bias of the respondents is another limitation.

Review of Literature:

Mc Luhan & Powers (1989) comment that the telephone creates instantaneous and immediate contact, much unlike the far more advanced means of communication. A majority of the telephone users look upon the telephone as a two edged sword. They simultaneously enjoy the power that it gives them to be able to connect with the world.

In this regard, Steel & Reisch (1993) addressed the concept of “telephone apprehension”. People may be apprehensive about using the phone maybe because they are afraid to communicate as against freuds classic theory (1946) of defence mechanisms, the exact opposite. The telephone has become an instrument for hostility and aggression.

Fielding & Hartley (1987) believe that in “non – seeing” conversation, people are depersonalized, task – oriented, stilted, extremist and uncompromising.

Such proposals strongly support Nobles (1987) previously reported findings that telephones are most preferred to face – to – face communication. Even though most people believe that the telephone is an invasion of privacy because one is compelled to answer. This concept is known as “telephone obedience”. But, by and large, telephone users feel that the phone helps to alleviate loneliness as it brings one into contact with outside world.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Particulars		No of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	161	67.08
	Female	79	32.92
	Total	240	100
Age	Less than 20 years	41	17.08
	20 to 30 years	80	33.33
	30 to 40 years	65	27.08
	40 to 50 years	33	13.75
	Above 50 years	21	8.75
	Total	240	100
Educational qualification	Post Graduates	93	38.75
	Graduates	116	48.33
	Other (High School, Hr. Sec., etc.)	31	12.92
	Total	240	100
Occupation	Government	41	17.08
	Private	82	34.17
	Business	85	35.42
	Others	32	13.33
	Total	240	100
Usage of broadband	Personal	112	46.67
	Business	76	31.67
	Both	52	21.67
	Total	240	100
Frequency of Getting	Regularly online	57	23.75

Connected	Once in a day	73	30.42
	Once in a Week	53	22.08
	Rarely (not specific)	57	23.75
	Total	240	100
Satisfaction on branded broadband has excellent uploading & downloading quality	Highly Satisfied	60	25
	Satisfied	97	40.42
	Neutral	24	10
	Dissatisfied	38	15.83
	Highly Dissatisfied	21	8.75
	Total	240	100
Satisfaction on branded broadband internet service has excellent speed and connectivity	Highly Satisfied	76	31.67
	Satisfied	94	39.17
	Neutral	5	2.08
	Dissatisfied	32	13.33
	Highly Dissatisfied	33	13.75
	Total	240	100
Satisfaction on provision of adequate network coverage	Highly Satisfied	56	23.33
	Satisfied	112	46.67
	Neutral	6	2.5
	Dissatisfied	34	14.17
	Highly Dissatisfied	32	13.33
	Total	240	100
Satisfaction towards resolving problems skillfully by the service provider	Highly Satisfied	84	35
	Satisfied	98	40.83
	Neutral	10	4.17
	Dissatisfied	20	8.33
	Highly Dissatisfied	28	11.67
	Total	240	100

From the above table it is clear that most (67.08%) of the respondents are male and 32.92% of the respondents are female. (33.33%) of the respondents belong the age between 20 and 30 years, followed by 27.08% of the respondents belong the age from 30 to 40 years, 17.08% of the respondents belong the age less than 20 years, 13.75% of the respondents belong the between 40 and 50 years and the remaining 8.75% of the respondents belong the age above 50 years. (48.33%) of the respondents are graduates, 38.75% of the respondents are post graduates and the remaining 12.92% of the respondents are qualified with others such as High School, Higher Secondary, Diploma, ITI, etc. (35.42%) of the respondents are involved in business closely followed by the respondents (34.17%) working in private sector, 17.08% of the respondents are government servants and the remaining 13.33% of the respondents are having other occupations (Service Sector, Professionals, etc.) (46.67%) of the respondents stated they used their broad band for personal purposes, while 31.67% of the respondents revealed that they used their broadband for business purposes and the remaining and the remaining 21.67% of the respondents used the broadband services for personal and business purposes. 30.42% of the respondents get connected with the broadband once in a day, 23.75% of the respondents getting connected regularly and rarely (not specific) respectively and the remaining 22.08% of the respondents are getting connected once in a week. (40.42%) of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband has excellent uploading and downloading quality, while 25% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 15.83% of the respondents are dissatisfied, 10% of the respondents had neutral opinion and the remaining 8.75% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied. 39.17% of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband has excellent speed and connectivity, while 31.67% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 13.75% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied, 13.33% of the respondents are dissatisfied and the remaining 2.08% of the respondents had neutral opinion. 46.67% of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband has adequate network coverage, while 23.33% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 14.17% of the respondents are dissatisfied, 13.33% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and the remaining 2.50% of the respondents had neutral opinion. 40.83% of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband towards resolving problems skillfully by the service provider, while 35% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 11.67% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied, 8.33% of the respondents are dissatisfied and the remaining 4.17% of the respondents had neutral opinion.

Findings:

- ✓ Most (67.08%) of the respondents are male
- ✓ Maximum (33.33%) of the respondents belong the age between 20 and 30 years
- ✓ Nearly half (48.33%) of the respondents are graduates

- ✓ Maximum (35.42%) of the respondents are involved in business
- ✓ Majority (40.42%) of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband has excellent uploading and downloading quality
- ✓ 39.17% of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband has excellent speed and connectivity
- ✓ 46.67% of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband has adequate network coverage.
- ✓ 40.83% of the respondents are satisfied towards the branded broadband towards resolving problems skillfully by the service provider.

Suggestions:

On the basis of the analysis conducted, the following Suggestions have been drawn. The major concern of the study was to assess the level of satisfaction of broadband users in Coimbatore. To achieve the stipulated objectives, the study used data collected through self administered questionnaire from 240 respondents. Improve marketing strategies to check whether the product is meeting expectations and can ask the customer for any product (or) service improvement suggestions and any specific disappointments. The management can contact the customer from time to time with suggestions about improved product uses / new product features. Some of the respondents also insisted on better connectivity and network facilities to avoid frequent disconnections faced by the respondents. Few of the respondents felt the network are feeble and the uploading and downloading is found to be poor. It is therefore suggested that the company may install more number of towers to deal with connectivity problem.

Conclusion:

A comparison made to find out the broadband users in Coimbatore is increased due to service availability and the aspects due to stiff competition from other broadband service providers in the market. The ability of an enterprise to management knowledge as an asset is to survive in a global business environment market Research, a systematic gathering, recording and analyzing of data about any (problems) activity to relating of goods and services. And act as one of the pillars of knowledge management. Few of the respondents feel that the billing by the service provider is exorbitant and they may intend to change the service provider in future.

References:

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2. Dale Hatfield, Michele H. Jackson, Tom Lookabaugh Scott Savage, Doug C. Sicker, Donald Waldman, (2008), Broadband Internet Access, Awareness, and Use: Analysis of United States Household Data, University of Colorado, Boulder
3. DSL or cable modem rates as being sufficiently high to be called broadband. For instance, Technet define broadband as 100 Mbps.
4. While recognizing there is variation in the bit rates used by academia, industry and policy makers, we employ the FCC's (2001) definition of high speed services (at least 200 kbps in at least one direction), which is consistent with DSL and cable modems.